

Lecturers' Job Satisfaction, Job Performance and Students' Academic Achievements in Private Universities in North Central States, Nigeria

Idogho Joshua

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Nasarawa State University, Keffi

Abstract

This research work is on lecturers' job satisfaction, job performance and students' academic achievements in private universities in North Central States, Nigeria. The research emphasizes how a good work environment, improved communication, sufficient provision of instructional materials and high financial motivation can lead to an increase in job satisfaction, which will in turn improve the job performance of lecturers and further enhance students' academic achievements. Four objectives and four research questions were answered, including the testing of four hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Theories were considered in this study, namely, Work Adjustment Theory as proposed by Loftquist, Dawis and Kanter in 1967, Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Need Theory (1954) and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959). Forty (40) empirical studies were reviewed on lecturers' job satisfaction, job performance and students' academic achievements. A descriptive survey research design was used. The population of this study is 19,458, which consists of 9,446 academic staff and 10,102 non-academic staff in all the 23 private universities within the six (6) states in North Central States, Nigeria. The simple random sampling procedure was adopted in determining the sample size. The sample size stood at 1,960, which consists of 945 academic staff and 1,015 non-academic staff, representing 10% of the 9,446 academic staff and 10,102 non-academic staff in the private universities within the six (6) states in North Central States, Nigeria. The Questionnaire on Relationship among Lecturers' Job Satisfaction, Job Performance and Students' Academic Achievements (QRLJSJPSAA) was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistical tool. The finding reveals that a good work environment, improved communication, sufficient provision of instructional materials and high financial motivation can lead to an increase in job satisfaction, which will in turn improve the job performance of lecturers and further enhance students' academic achievements in private universities in North Central States, Nigeria. The study recommends that private university administrators at the state level, especially HoDs, should utilize the available working conditions, which will enhance lecturers' job performance in teaching and learning and further improve students' academic achievements in private universities in North Central States, Nigeria.

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By

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Figure 1